

THE TECHNOLOGY OF PLASMA-ARC ATOMIZATION OF CURRENT-CARRYING SOLID WIRES FOR TITANIUM POWDER PRODUCTION

*Strohonov D.,
Tereshchenko O.,
Burlachenko O.,
Korzhyk V.,
Ganushchak O.,
Konoreva O.*

*E.O. Paton Electric Welding Institute, National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine
Kyiv, Ukraine*

ABSTRACT

Currently, due to the rapid development of additive manufacturing, there is an urgent need to produce high-quality spherical granules and powders of titanium and titanium alloys with special properties, namely, a high degree of sphericity, the absence of external and internal defects, a given particle size distribution, etc. The possibility of obtaining high-quality spherical powders from technical titanium using plasma-arc spraying technology of CP-Ti (Grade 2) current-carrying wire with a diameter of 1.6 mm has been experimentally confirmed.

Keywords: additive technologies, plasma-arc atomization, spheroidization, granules, powders.

The intensive development of additive technologies (AT) for printing titanium alloy parts by DED (Direct Energy Deposition) and PBF (Powder Bed Fusion) methods requires the creation of special materials in the form of spherical powders with a specified particle size composition (mostly less than 53 μm) and strict requirements for the shape of particles (coefficient of sphericity) with the presence of a minimum number of defective particles [1, 2]. One of the most promising methods of obtaining such powders is the plasma-arc atomization of current-carrying solid titanium wires with diameters of 1.0 to 3.2 mm [3, 4].

At this time, there are not enough investigations on the effect of the parameters of plasma-arc atomization mode on particle size distribution, chemical composition and technological properties of the powder, etc. Thus, the work aims to study the influence of the parameters of the plasma-arc atomization process of current-carrying titanium wire and to confirm the possibility of obtaining high-quality spherical powders during its atomization.

Figure 1 shows a schematic representation of the plasma-arc atomization process of the current-carrying

wire. An essence of the process of plasma-arc atomization process lies in melting of the tip of the current-carrying solid wire (anode) which is entered in a zone of high-speed plasma jet and further fragmentation of the melt stripping from a wire end. An arc burns between a non-consumable tungsten cathode and a current-carrying wire (anode) being fed through a plasma torch nozzle. Working (plasma-forming) gas entering an operating chamber is heated with an electric arc and comes out from the nozzle in form of a plasma jet. An open section of a discharge out of the plasma-forming nozzle is blown concentrically by a gas flow coming out of a circular gap between the plasma torch nozzles. Among the peculiarities of this method is the fact that melting and jet atomization of the wire material is carried out by argon plasma, meanwhile melt fragmentation and acceleration of dispersed particles is intensified by a jet of cold concurrent gas. This provides minimum losses on evaporation of wire material (up to 2 %), obtaining the optimum fraction composition of the disperse phase, reaching a near-sonic velocity by the particles of atomization material, etc [5, 6].

Fig. 1. Schematic representation (a) [7] and visualization (b) of the plasma-arc atomization process for the production of Ti powders

The technological experiments were carried out using a plasma-arc atomization unit PLAZER-50 [8], which was modified for the realization of the process of

atomization of titanium wire and powder production (fig. 1(b)).

Table 1

Technical parameters of plasma-arc atomization unit PLAZER-50	
Energy consumption, kVA no more	50
The voltage of the three-phase alternating current supply network with a frequency of 50 Hz, V	380
No-load voltage, V	160
Operating current adjustment range, A	100 – 400
Operating voltage adjustment range, V	60 – 125
The longest duration of inclusion, PV%	100
Argon consumption at a pressure of 0.6 MPa, nm ³ /h	8
Wire feed speed, m/min	5 – 15
Cooling of the plasmatron	water
The resource of the plasmatron nozzle and cathode, hours of machine time, no less	100
Overall dimensions, mm:	
- power sources	501 x 478 x 503
- control cabinets	605 x 605 x 1600

Indicated equipment was used for the examination of the particle size distribution in the atomization of titanium wire (anode) CP-Ti (Grade 2) of 1.6 mm diameter (table 2).

Table 2.

Chemical composition of titanium wire CP-Ti (Grade 2)					
Element, wt. %					
Ti	Fe	O	C	N	H
≥ 98.9	≤ 0.30	≤ 0.25	≤ 0.080	≤ 0.030	≤ 0.015

According to earlier obtained practical data, an optimum mode was selected using a criterion of visual assessment of the shape of the plasma jet at its reaching a minimum opening angle and process stability. It was

used for a corresponding change of the parameters of mode to determine the effect of each of them on the change of the particle granulometric composition. High grade argon II according to ISO 14175–2008“Welding

consumables — gases and gas mixtures for fusion welding and allied processes” was used as a plasma-forming gas, nozzle diameter was 3 mm.

Variable atomization parameters were within the following limits: current — 250-400 A, arc voltage — 80-125 V, consumption of plasma-forming gas — 125 l/min, wire feed rate – 10-20 m/min, the gap between the cathode and the anode - 10 mm.

The particle size distribution of laboratory batches of powder was carried out by the method of dry sieve analysis according to the methodology of DSTU 2640-94 Metallic powders. Determination of particle size by dry sieving (ISO 4497:1983, GOST 18318-94) using a

sieve analyzer AS-200U (ROTAP) with a set of sieves, μm : 25...45, 45...63, 63...75, 75...100, 100...125, 125...160, 160...200, 200...250, 250...315.

An experimental study of the particle size distribution (fig. 2) of the obtained powders showed that by changing the parameters of the plasma-arc atomization process (plasma torch power from 20 to 50 kW), it is possible to regulate the particle size distribution within wide limits. In all cases, the main fraction of the powder is the fraction of 25...160 μm , which is 85...90% of the total mass of the powder. It should also be noted that when atomizing at a power of 50 kW, the output of the finely dispersed fraction <45 μm can be up to 50 wt.%.

Fig. 2. The effect of the plasma torch power on the particle size distribution of titanium powder

The results of research on the morphology of the obtained powder showed that in all the investigated

powder samples, the particles generally have the correct spherical shape (fig. 3), but there are few satellites and single particles of irregular shape.

Fig. 3. Morphology (a) and cross-section (b) of obtained titanium powder CP-Ti (Grade 2)

The results of the study of the chemical composition of the obtained powder showed that it

corresponds to the original chemical composition of the consumable wire (table 3).

Table 3.

The content of oxygen, nitrogen, and carbon impurities in the CP-Ti (Grade 2) powder (wt. %).

oxygen	nitrogen	carbon
0.293	0.076	0.078

In this way, it shown the possibility of obtaining spherical powders of titanium with a minimum number of defective particles through the application of plasma-arc atomization of current-carrying wire.

Conclusions

1. Current progress in the field of additive manufacturing has shown that there are currently no highly efficient and productive methods for producing spherical metal titanium powders. Such general industrial methods as plasma rotating electrode process and gas atomization have several disadvantages, their use is limited, primarily low productivity. One of the most promising methods of obtaining such powders is the plasma-arc atomization of current-carrying solid titanium wires with diameters of 1.0 to 3.2 mm.

2. The possibility of obtaining high-quality spherical powders from technical titanium using plasma-arc spraying technology of CP-Ti (Grade 2) current-carrying wire with a diameter of 1.6 mm has been experimentally confirmed.

3. The study of the particles size distribution of the obtained powder allows its use for the main AT methods, for example, selective laser melting and sintering, which successfully uses powder fractions up to 53 μm , electron beam melting and plasma melting deposition 45...160 μm , etc.

Acknowledgments

The work was carried out with the support of project "Strategic project of the Academy of Sciences of Guangdong Province" (GDAS'Project of Science and Technology Development, 2020GDASYL-20200301001), China.

References

1. Sun P., Fang Z., Zhang Y. et al. Review of the Methods for the Production of Spherical Ti and Ti Alloy Powder. *JOM*. V. 69. 2017. P. 1853–1860. (<https://doi.org/10.1007/s11837-017-2513-5>).

2. Chen G., Zhao S., Tan P. et al. A comparative study of Ti-6Al-4V powders for additive manufacturing by gas atomization, plasma rotating electrode process and plasma atomization. *Powder Technology*. V.333. 2018. P. 38-46. (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.powtec.2018.04.013>)

3. Yurtukan E., Unal R., Theoretical and experimental investigation of Ti alloy powder production using low-power plasma torches. *Transactions of Nonferrous Metals Society of China*. V. 32. 2022. P. 175-191. ([https://doi.org/10.1016/S1003-6326\(21\)65786-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1003-6326(21)65786-2))

4. Entezarian M., Allaire F., Tsantrizos P. et al. Plasma atomization: A new process for the production of fine, spherical powders. *JOM*. V. 48. 1996. P. 53–55. (<https://doi.org/10.1007/BF03222969>)

5. Korzhyk V.M., Khaskin V.Yu., Yuhui Yao, Demianov O.I., Strogonov D.V., Shcheretskiy V.O. Influence of accompanying compressing air flow on the coating structure and properties in plasma-arc spraying by consumable current-conducting wire. *The Paton Welding Journal*. № 2. 2022. P. 3-10. (<https://doi.org/10.37434/tpwj2022.02.01>)

6. Korzhyk V.M., Strogonov D.V., Burlachenko O.M., Tunik A.Yu., Ganushchak O.V., Hrishchenko O.P. Effectiveness of the process of plasma-arc spheroidization of current-conducting titanium wire. *The Paton Welding Journal*. № 3. 2023. P. 33-41. (<https://doi.org/10.37434/tpwj2023.03.05>)

7. <https://www.carpenteradditive.com/resources>

8. Korzhyk V.M., Strogonov D.V., Burlachenko O.M., Ganushchak O.V., Voitenko O.M. New generation unit for plasma-arc deposition of coatings and spraying of current-conducting wire materials. *The Paton Welding Journal*. № 10. 2023. P. 35-42. (<https://doi.org/10.37434/tpwj2023.10.06>)